

**Fairness & Wellbeing
Commission**

Session 2: Through the lens of Doncaster's Older Residents

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Local Context
Data

The 2021 census found that Doncaster had 59,867 (19.4%) people aged 65+ living in the borough.

% of Doncaster Residents Aged 65+ by MSOA			
Tickhill & Wadworth	33.7%	Hatfield West	19.1%
Cadeby, Hickleton & Hampole	29.8%	Stainforth	18.55
Armthorpe South	29.8%	Mexborough East	18.1%
Kirk Sandall & Barnby Dunn	27.2%	Conisbrough South	17.8%
Old Cantley, Auckley & Finningley	26.1%	Bawtry, Austerfield & Hayfield	17.7 %
Bessacarr & Bawtry Road	25.9%	Scawthorpe	17.7%
Bessacarr Grange & Lakeside	23.9%	Bentley Rise	17.7%
Sprotbrough	23.8%	Mexborough West	17.3%
Rossington	23.7%	Wheatley Hills	17%
Warmsworth, Braithwell & Stainton	23.6%	Armthorpe North	16%
Cusworth	22.9%	Intake	15.9%
Cantley Park	22.8%	Belle Vue & Town Fields	15.3%
Carcroft	22.5%	Adwick Le Street & Woodlands	15.2%
Thorne	22.2%	Moorends	15.1%
Edenthorpe & Mere Lane	21.5%	New Rossington	15.1%
Hatfield East	21.4%	Bentley & Toll Bar	14.4%
Conisbrough North	19.9%	Balby Carr	10%
Balby South	19.8%	Central Doncaster & Hyde Park	9.1%
Askern	19.5%		

19.4% of people in Doncaster **LAD** are aged 65 years and over

Population Change

Population change (%) by age group in Doncaster, 2011 to 2021

- increase in people aged 65 years and over
- decrease in people aged 15 to 64 years
- decrease in children aged under 15 years.

It is estimated that by 2036 Doncaster will have over 80,000 residents aged over 65

This data is based on the 2018 population projections, and will certainly be rebased in the light of the 2021 census. The expectation is that, on average, the number of people aged 65+ will increase by around 1200 each year, and around 650 a year for people aged 85+.

The average deprivation score derived from the Census deprivation measure was 20.7%.

There are 29 LSOAs* that are both deprived and have a high proportion of people aged 65+.

10,548 people age 65+ live in these areas as demonstrated in the top right quarter of the graph below.

*LSOAs are a Census geography each LSOA has, on average around 1,550 residents. There are 199 LSOAs in Doncaster.

The 2019 Index of Multiple Deprivation included an extra domain: **Income Deprivation affecting Older People Index (IDAOP)**.

Doncaster is the **85th** most deprived local authority in England, out of a total of 317 authorities in this category.

The IDAOP is measured at LSOA level.

54.3% of people aged 60+ are in the nationally defined most deprived areas in the country

	% in National Decile
Most Deprived	5.3
2	12.8
3	11.2
4	13.6
5	11.4
6	8.9
7	11.3
8	12.5
9	7.3
Least Deprived	5.7

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Healthy life expectancy at 65

Health life expectancy in Doncaster has been lower than the national average for several years.

Over the last 4 years HLE has been falling for both men and women. In the period 2018-20 it fell below 8 years for those aged 65 in both men and women.

A01a - Healthy life expectancy at 65 (Male)

A01a - Healthy life expectancy at 65 (Male)

A01a - Healthy life expectancy at 65 (Female)

A01a - Healthy life expectancy at 65 (Female)

Doncaster has the Lowest Healthy Life Expectancy for those aged 65 of all its statistical neighbours.

The 2021 Census recorded 266,798 households* in Doncaster. 13.5% of these have a older person (aged 66+) living alone, and 23.0% are households with all members aged 66+.

18.8% of households were living in fuel poverty in 2020. This data cannot be broken down by age.

Communities with high levels of fuel poverty and higher proportions of people aged 65+ can be identified.

The 15 communities detailed in the above graph have 50% or more of households with people age 66+ only living in them.

18 LSOAs have high fuel poverty and high numbers of older people.

59,867 people aged 65+ live in areas of high fuel poverty.

* A 'household' is defined as either one person living alone, or a group of people living at the same address and sharing both cooking facilities and a living room or dining area.

1 in 10 Doncaster Residents provide regular unpaid care

A person is a provider of unpaid care if they look after or give help or support to family members or others because of long-term physical or mental ill health or disability, or problems related to old age.

Caring can have a significant impact on health and wellbeing. 60% of carers report a long-term health condition or disability compared to 50% non-carers
(Carers UK analysis of GP Patient Survey 2021).

No of Doncaster residents providing unpaid care by age band (Census 2021)

Doncaster Residents providing unpaid care by age band and hours of unpaid care (census 2021)

Age Band	up to 9 hours		10-19 hours		20-34 hours		35-49 hours		50+ hours	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
55 to 59	1,290	5.9	570	2.6	385	1.7	510	2.3	1,040	4.7
60 to 64	1,055	5.4	470	2.4	350	1.8	450	2.3	995	5.1
65 to 69	565	3.4	330	2.0	245	1.5	190	1.1	1,000	6.0
70 to 74	365	2.2	235	1.4	175	1.1	100	0.6	1,050	6.4
75 to 79	180	1.6	115	1.0	100	0.9	95	0.8	765	6.6
80 to 84	115	1.4	65	0.8	65	0.8	60	0.7	585	7.3
85 to 89	45	0.9	30	0.6	30	0.6	20	0.4	300	6.0
90+	10	0.4	10	0.4	10	0.4	<5		105	4.3

Caring comes with additional costs that can have a significant impact on carers' finances and many carers suffer financial hardship. 44% of working-age adults who are caring for 35 hours or more a week are in poverty.
(Joseph Rowntree Foundation, UK Poverty 2022).

Age band	Number of residents
55 to 59	3,795
60 to 64	3,320
65 to 69	2,330
70 to 74	1,925
75 to 79	1,255
80 to 84	890
85 to 89	425
90+	140

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*"I can go two or three days
without talking to anybody."*

Janet, Doncaster

There is a strong relationship between
loneliness and poor mental and physical
health.

Social Isolation

In 2020 38% of adult social care users (aged 65+) in Doncaster felt they had as much social contact as they would like; this is slightly below the England and Regional rates of 43% and the lowest local rate since 2015.

Social Isolation: percentage of adult social care users who have as much social contact as they would like (65+ years)

The proportion of respondents who completed the Social Care User Survey question "Thinking about how much contact you've had with people you like, which of the following statements best describes your social situation?", answering "I have as much social contact as I want with people I like".

38%

of adult social care users have as much
social contact as they would like

Dementia is a syndrome characterised by a decline in intellectual function and is usually diagnosed to those in later life.

Dementia rates in Doncaster are:

worse than national average

Rates of dementia in Doncaster have remained roughly stable since 2016.

Doncaster residents are similarly likely to be diagnosed with dementia than national average.

The recorded dementia prevalence is the number of people with dementia recorded on GP practice registers as a proportion of the people (all ages) registered at each GP practice. Where allocated to a local authority boundary this was done using the postcode of the practice

Doncaster has reported around 3.9% of its population aged 65+ has dementia.

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Local Insight Summary

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Doncaster Talks Survey Responses

“We in certain areas have been deprived of our bus service. The people in lower end Norton, Old Campsall and upper Askern village. These areas cover a lot of elderly, disabled and vulnerable people and we are being cut off from life. Only a few can drive only a few can afford taxi trips so how is that fair?”

“Not enough provision for social activity for the elderly. Many are stuck at home, lonely and isolated. Need more day centres, disabled transport”

“I am 78 years old, an Army Veteran of 22 years’ service for Queen & Country but feel let down by the Hearing Aid centre in Sandringham Road. I have been on their waiting list for new Hearing Aids & hearing test since April of last year 2021. Boots are advertising a hearing aid service at £29 per month for 4 years, that’s £1392, Unbelievable. I wrote to my GP over a month ago about my problem but have not had a reply”

“What is unfair about life in Doncaster “	% of responses
Unfair investment by area	18.2
Anti-social behaviour	10.4
Public Transport	10.4
Private Transport	7.3
Perception of Place	6.8
Local Govt	6.8
Intergenerational unfairness	5.7

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Insight from Workshops

Dance On, The Point

Three interlinking priorities for attendees of Dance On

Citizens Advice Doncaster

Access to information

- Weary of digital due to scams
- Won't "google it"
- Face-to-face in trusted places is effective

Access to services

- Transport is key barrier
- Expense of day services
- Safety in town centre
- Community-level service delivery makes it easier

Challenges

- Crux is often loneliness
- Pandemic effect - loss of habits & confidence leading to isolation
- Income maximisation: £9mn unclaimed pension credit
- Pride & cautiousness means more likely to accept difficult situation

Tipping points

- Divorce
- Death of a partner
- Family relationship breakdown
- Health issues

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Insight from Workshops

Askarne SMILE Day Centre

Social Isolation

- Need for social/recreational activities available through the Day Centre

Access to services

- Limited access locally to services including banks and post offices
- Increased cost of accessing services

Public Transport

- Accessibility of park and rides for wheelchair users

Crime and ASB

- Concern around ASB in local area and littering
- Fear around speeding and road safety for pedestrians

Housing

- Damp and mould issues untreated for a long period of time -> health issues

Live Inclusive Disability Group*

Crime and ASB

- concern around safety and ASB in City Centre
- disabilities/health conditions can exacerbate feelings of vulnerability.

Access to Services and Healthcare

- access to and continuity of care
- need for light touch support alongside specialist support

Transport

- mixed experience of public transport
- concern around bus updates for the digitally excluded

Recreation and leisure

- limited social offer for the disabled beyond DICE

*Not all members of this group were older age residents

Comments from Hatfield Community Library, Dance On, and Monday Smile a While, Thorne

"I try to keep myself busy since the wife died, this group has been really important in that"

"We set up this bridge group after realising there were a lot of activities that catered for lonely ladies and less so for the men"

"It takes 2 buses to get into town to get to the library from Hexthorpe. I'm lucky that I can get a lift from family but others are not so fortunate."

"Coming to Smile a While is my only opportunity to see people all week since my husband died"

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Wider Engagement

Localities Engagement 2022

Priorities for residents aged 60+ from minority ethnic backgrounds who were engaged as part of Your Life Doncaster consultation by Localities team:

- English language support
- Improved access to Services
- More frequent, better connected and affordable transport
- More opportunities to attend community groups
- More done to tackle ASB & Crime in their area
- Making local places more accessible for those with disabilities
- Cleaner streets in their area

Age Friendly Survey 2023

12. In your opinion, how good and accessible are the following themes in Doncaster?
Rate on a scale from 1-5 with one being very poor and five being excellent.

■ 1 - Very Poor ■ 2 - Poor ■ 3 - Average ■ 4 - Good ■ 5 - Excellent

Age Friendly Festival Autumn 2021

“When I’m older I hope that ...

- ... I can be healthy enough to live a healthy life, mentally and physically. Not be lonely, have enough friends to go out to do activities with and go on holidays and days out.”
- ... Elderly people will be treated as individuals with individual interests, personalities and needs. This should be understood and respected.”
- ... I can live a healthy and active lifestyle when/if I retire. I am hoping there will be access to events/activities available at any age as I grow older, to enable making friendships and trying new hobbies/skills in adult life.”
- ... There are plenty of places to go to meet up with friends and people with similar interests. That I will have enough money to live on. That medical care will be excellent and public transport will be cheap and plentiful. That I will be able to live a long, happy and healthy life and to continue to get out and do the things I like to do.”
- ... My friends and family are happy and safe. The world is a peaceful and more understanding place. That I remain confident to go out and see people, my health is OK and I’m not forgotten.”

Dementia Insight Healthwatch 2022

- “Didn’t find anyone to help with paperwork for financial support. Asked various organisation if they could identify any activities or clubs all said they didn’t know”
- “Very trying to get the care that was needed, trying to work with professionals slow. Too many different departments”
- “It was getting someone to take me seriously because I could tell things weren’t right”
- “It needs to be holistic to the individual. My mother can’t cope with everything and sort through forms and paperwork. Way too much paperwork information, not even relevant. The cost. If people can’t afford the services of day care. Befriender, they are stuck at home with unable to see anyone.”
- “Transport to the day centres by St Leger is invaluable but unreliable. Despite paying for a full day at a centre you can not get a bus early to get you there. Also they bring home early. The drivers are great but needs more and better offer.”